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Impact of In-Consistency between the Climate Model and its Initial Conditions on

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1 **Abstract**

2 We investigated the influence of dynamical in-consistency of initial conditions on the predictive skill of decadal
3 climate predictions. The investigation builds on the fully coupled global model “Coupled GCM for Earth
4 Simulator” (CFES). In two separate experiments, the ocean component of the coupled model is full-field
5 initialized with two different initial fields from either the same coupled model CFES or the GECCO2 Ocean
6 Synthesis while the atmosphere is initialized from CFES in both cases. Differences between both experiments
7 show that higher SST forecast skill is obtained when initializing with CDA initial conditions (CIH) instead of
8 those from GECCO2 (GIH), with the most significant difference in skill obtained over the tropical Pacific at lead
9 year one. High predictive skill of SST over the tropical Pacific seen in CIH reflects the good reproduction of El
10 Niño events at lead year one. In contrast, GIH produces additional erroneous El Niño events. The tropical Pacific
11 skill differences between both runs can be rationalized in terms of the zonal momentum balance between the
12 wind stress and pressure gradient force, which characterizes the upper equatorial Pacific. In GIH, the differences
13 between the oceanic and atmospheric state at initial time leads to imbalance between the zonal wind stress and
14 pressure gradient force over the equatorial Pacific, which leads to the additional pseudo El Niño events and
15 explains reduced predictive skill. The balance can be reestablished if anomaly initialization strategy is applied
16 with GECCO2 initial conditions and improved predictive skill in the tropical Pacific is observed at lead year one.
17 However, initializing the coupled model with self-consistent initial conditions leads to the highest skill of
18 climate prediction in the tropical Pacific by preserving the momentum balance between zonal wind stress and
19 pressure gradient force along the equatorial Pacific.

20 **Key words:** climate prediction, initialization, tropical Pacific, El Niño, momentum balance

1 **1. Introduction**

2 Since the inception of “decadal prediction” as a new field in climate research in the early 2000s (Vera et al. 2010;
3 Meehl et al. 2009), much effort has been devoted to provide reliable information of the climate system in terms
4 of forecasts of the coming decades. Being a joint initial and boundary value problem (e.g. Hawkins and Sutton
5 2009; Murphy et al. 2010), obtaining skillful decadal predictions remains a major challenge, partly due to
6 uncertainty in the initial climate state the model starts from, due to imperfection of climate models, or even due
7 to lacking information about future external forcing.

8 Despite remaining problems, earlier studies have demonstrated convincingly the improvement in decadal climate
9 predictions, which result from initializing models by estimates of the observed climate state (e.g. CMIP5; Taylor
10 et al. 2012). In general terms, initialization encompasses an initialization strategy and a reanalysis that provides
11 the initial state of the model. How to best estimate the initial conditions and what best practices are while
12 initializing a model from those estimates still remain the subject of major investigations. Modeling groups have
13 in particular devoted much effort into exploring different techniques and methodology for initialization (e.g.
14 CMIP5, Meehl et al. 2009, 2014; Murphy et al. 2007). On seasonal time scales, Magnusson et al. (2012) showed
15 that higher predictive skill was provided by full-state initialization in comparison to anomaly initialization, while
16 Smith et al. (2012) in the context of decadal predictions reported regionally more skillful predictions in hindcasts
17 with anomaly initialization. In contrast, a recent study by Hazeleger et al. (2013) revealed no significant
18 difference in decadal predictability between the two different methods. Polkova et al. (2014) obtained the highest
19 SST predictive skill for flux corrected hindcasts combined with full field initialization due to smaller biases in
20 regions of a deep mixed layer, which carry the predictive memory. Nevertheless, so far the flux correction
21 strategy has not been adopted by any of the climate models in CMIP5 (Meehl et al. 2014).

22 With the full field initialization, any model is strongly constrained with a realistic representation of the climatic
23 system at the beginning of the forecasts (e.g. Bellucci et al. 2012; Smith et al. 2013), which typically differs from
24 its native model climatology. In response, this leads to an initial shock at the beginning of forecasts (Balmaseda
25 and Anderson 2009) and the model bias grows as the forecasts evolve (Pierce et al. 2004; Smith et al. 2013). So
26 far, the most commonly used source of initial conditions is estimations of a few climate components (e.g. the
27 ocean, atmosphere), mostly derived from combining observations with atmospheric or oceanic general
28 circulation models. However, to offer the best forecast skill, all the elements of the climate system shall be
29 considered, including the atmosphere, the ocean, sea ice and land parameters (Doblas-Reyes et al. 2011; Smith et

1 al. 2007; Troccoli and Palmer 2007). Such initialization can result from a coupled system estimating initial
2 conditions all at once. Reducing the initial shock may also help to improve the forecasts skill with the full state
3 initialization strategy. One way to pursue is to employ analyses derived from coupled data assimilation system as
4 initial conditions (Laloyaux et al. 2015, Mulholland et al. 2015). Ideally this should be obtained using the same
5 model that is used during the forecast step and should be done in a way that the model is kept in dynamical
6 balance thereby eliminating the initial model shock.

7 Several approaches are feasible to perform coupled data assimilation, including coupled Ensemble Kalman
8 filters (EnKF) as well as fully coupled adjoint data assimilation schemes (see Stammer et al. 2015 for a review of
9 assimilation approaches). As an example, Karspeck et al. (2014) used an EnKF based coupled assimilation
10 approach to initialize decadal predictions. Results were of mixed quality, however, possibly because a state
11 estimated with a coupled EnKF becomes dynamically inconsistent with the coupled system. A superior approach
12 therefore seems to use, instead of a filter, a smoother, which estimates only model parameters such that the
13 resulting initial state remains dynamically consistent with the model. Such a coupled adjoint system was realized
14 by Sugiura et al. (2008) who demonstrate that by assimilating historical observations (ocean, atmosphere, ice and
15 land surface) into a fully coupled ocean-atmosphere model “Coupled GCM for Earth Simulator” (CFES), better
16 initial conditions can be derived since the initial shock in the full-state initialization strategy is reduced simply
17 because of the dynamical consistency between the model and initial conditions. By controlling air-sea-land
18 fluxes through the optimization of the bulk formulae parameters, coupled model errors are reduced. In
19 comparison to the initialization from ocean-only assimilation, improved predictive skill is found on seasonal to
20 interannual time scales.

21 Because in the context of decadal climate prediction a self-consistent initial condition (derived through a coupled
22 model) has not been used, the impact of the consistency between the model and its initial conditions has not yet
23 been explored. To what extent existing forecast skills on decadal time scales could be further improved through
24 the development of coupled data assimilation/forecast systems remains to be investigated. A related investigation
25 is performed here, realized by initializing the fully coupled climate system CFES with (1) self-consistent initial
26 conditions and (2) non-consistent initial conditions. Since with the dynamically self-consistent initial conditions,
27 the model will suffer less from initial shocks and artificial model drift, more skillful predictions than initialized
28 with non-consistent initial conditions are expected. Results will help to identify the existence of additional
29 potential skill, which can result from coupled adjoint estimation approaches.

1 The remaining paper is structured as follows: Section 2 provides a description of the coupled model, the
2 experimental setup, as well as the statistical methods used for skill assessment. The performances of climate
3 predictive skill based on one or the other initialization scheme are evaluated in Section 3. Section 4 investigates
4 the underlying mechanisms relevant to predictive skill and concluding remarks are provided in Section 5.

5 **2. Model and experimental setup**

6 **2.1 The fully coupled global climate system CFES**

7 To explore the skill of decadal predictions, we use the fully coupled climate model CFES developed by “Japan
8 Agency for Marine-Earth Science and Technology” (JAMSTEC). CFES is composed of the atmospheric GCM
9 for the Earth Simulator (AFES, Ohfuchi et al. 2004) and the Ocean-Sea Ice GCM for the Earth Simulator
10 (OIFES, Komori et al. 2004). The resolution of the spectral AFES component horizontally is T42 (about 2.8° by
11 2.8°); in the vertical the model has 24 layers in σ coordinates. Embedded with a rectangular grid system, OIFES
12 has a global domain with horizontal resolution of 1° in both latitude and longitude, and 45 vertical layers
13 (Masuda et al. 2006; Sugiura et al. 2008).

14 For the decadal hindcasts, an updated model system forced with historical radiative forcing conditions including
15 greenhouse gas (GHG), aerosol and volcano, is used, based on the radiation code MstrnX (Nakajima et al. 2000).
16 Zonal averaged 2D-xy grid annual-mean GHGs (CH_4 , CO_2 , N_2O) and monthly volcano are taken from
17 historical and RCP4.5 scenario-based data in CMIP5, both vertically averaged. As is commonly used in global
18 warming simulations, radiative effects of volcanic ash (historical major volcanic eruptions) are also taken into
19 account. But instead of directly using concentration of volcanic ash, additional optical thickness for a specific
20 band of radiation spectrum at the lowest level of the model stratosphere is used. Aerosols (black and organic
21 carbon, dust, sulfur) used here are column integrated monthly-mean historical and RCP4.5 scenario-based
22 simulations in CMIP5. Since the version of MstrnX used does not calculate chlorofluorocarbon (CFC) effect, the
23 CFC values are set to zeros and ozone is set to 3-D monthly climatology.

24 **2.2 Experimental setups for CDA/GECCO2 initialized hindcasts**

25 We initialize the first set of hindcasts performed with the fully coupled climate model CFES with the state
26 provided by the Coupled Data Assimilation (CDA, Sugiura et al. 2008) itself. CDA is an estimation of the
27 coupled climate state obtained by assimilating ocean (SST, climatological data, altimetry and in-situ data) and
28 atmospheric data (National Centers for Environmental Prediction (NCEP) reanalysis) into the CFES model with

1 the 4D-VAR method. The coupled model was controlled by air-sea surface fluxes through the estimation of bulk
2 adjustment factors (control variables of sensible heat, latent heat, and momentum fluxes) and the oceanic state
3 every 6 months over 9 months long periods with overlapping windows. In the following we will refer to this set
4 of hindcasts as CDA initialized hindcasts (CIH).

5 To evaluate how consistent initial conditions impact the predictive skill, another set of hindcasts initialized with
6 the ocean synthesis from the project “German contribution to Estimating the Circulation and Climate of the
7 Ocean” (GECCO2, Köhl 2014), referred to as GECCO2 initialized hindcasts (GIH), is also carried out. Forced
8 with fluxes derived via bulk formulae from the atmospheric state of National Centers for Environmental
9 Prediction-National Center for Atmospheric Research (NCEP-NCAR) reanalysis, GECCO2 uses the adjoint
10 method to adjust the atmospheric state by assimilating available hydrographic and satellite data (Köhl 2014). The
11 properties used as the oceanic initial conditions are 3-D monthly mean temperature, salinity, velocity (both zonal
12 and meridional), and sea surface height. Since the GECCO2 uses a different grid (vertical, zonal and meridional)
13 and topography than the coupled CFES system, the GECCO2 fields are interpolated to the CEFS grid after
14 expanding with the nearest grid value towards the continent and bottom of ocean.

15 In both sets of hindcasts the atmospheric model is initialized with CDA and makes use of climatology of the
16 optimized bulk adjustment factors from CDA. Given the incompatibility of GECCO2 ocean estimation to the
17 atmospheric component of CFES, model biases arise in GIH and the climate of the forecast drifts, which will
18 impact the predictive skill (e.g. Smith et al. 2013). In order to evaluate the impact of the drift, an extra set of
19 hindcasts is conducted in which the ocean is initialized with GECCO2 through the anomaly initialization
20 approach (AGIH). The anomalies of GECCO2 are calculated with respect to the 1980-2006 mean and added to
21 the 1980-2006 climatology of an un-initialized 20C run that is externally forced only. The CDA synthesis is
22 available from 1980 to 2006 and all hindcast experiments that run over 9 years are initialized every year in
23 January from 1980 to 2006, each with one ensemble member. The list of experiments is summarized in Table 1.

24 **2.3 Metrics of skill evaluation**

25 To quantify to what extent the climate drift reduces if forecasts are initialized with self-consistent initial
26 conditions, the time evolutions of global-averaged (60°S-60°N) SST from the 3 sets of hindcasts CIH, GIH and
27 AGIH are compared with observations and CDA or GECCO2, respectively. The observations for SST are taken
28 from the UK Met Office Hadley Center dataset (HadISST; Rayner et al. 2003). As is indicated by the colored
29 lines in Fig 1, CIH drifts less from CDA (black) than GIH (colors) does with respect to GECCO2 (black), which

1 tends to be warm-biased after initialization and drifts towards a cold bias later on. With the anomaly
2 initialization strategy drifts are smaller than for the full-state initialization approach when initialized from
3 GECCO2. CDA uses 9-month assimilation windows during which bulk coefficients are adjusted to keep the
4 model close to the data and therefore to also minimize drift. Due to the succeeded restarts of the model, the CDA
5 trajectory is not perfectly continuous but the model drift is well controlled such that no apparent gaps become
6 visible. In contrast, CIH uses only a climatology bulk coefficients but additionally GHG forcing. These
7 differences could lead to a larger drift in CIH than CDA as is shown in the top panel of Fig 1 by the colored lines.
8 Despite this, with the full-state initialization approach, a smaller drift in CIH due to self-consistent initial
9 conditions can still be expected in terms of global SST values.

10 For a detailed evaluation of predictive skill, a posterior bias correction is needed with full-state initialized
11 hindcasts (ICPO 2011). We adopt the lead-time dependent mean-bias correction method before the assessment of
12 forecast skill (e.g., Polkova et al. 2014). The mean bias as a function of lead year is removed from the hindcasts
13 by subtracting the difference between the climatological average of hindcasts and that of observations on each
14 starting date at different lead years from the hindcasts of the same period. To assess the predictive skill of
15 hindcasts, two metrics are commonly used: the anomaly correlation coefficient (ACC) and the root mean square
16 error (RMSE). RMSE offers primary assessment on prediction skill (Tebaldi and Knutti 2007; Goddard et al.
17 2013) through the comparison between hindcasts and observations. To compare and assess the relative skill in
18 different forecast experiments, the root mean square error skill score (i.e. RMSS; Jolliffe and Stephenson 2003)
19 based on a set of RMSE from paired hindcasts (e.g. RMSS for CIH is $1 - \text{RMSE}_{\text{CIH}} / \text{RMSE}_{20c}$) was computed. The
20 resulting global map of RMSS in terms of annual mean SST (not shown) reveals no significant difference at the
21 first lead year between CIH and GIH, while errors are smaller over large areas of the ocean in the former than
22 the latter at lead year 2-5.

23 Since RMSE is sensitive to outliers and would lead to a possibility of large error (Collins 2002), another
24 measurement used here is the anomaly correlation coefficient (ACC), which is a scale-invariant measure of the
25 linear associations between the two sets of forecasts. The ACC skill measures only the phase difference between
26 the observations and forecasts experiment (Matei et al. 2012). Since ACC is sensitive to the trend, all the
27 variables are detrended first, following a period dependent linear-trend removal strategy (Kharin et al. 2012).
28 With this strategy, the long-term linear trend of the variable is firstly calculated from hindcasted fields over the
29 initialization period of 1980-2006 at different lead year for each grid point, employing the least square statistical

1 method. Afterwards, the trend is subtracted from the hindcasts over lead years for each grid point. The
2 application of detrending avoids an overestimation of the performance of the hindcasts. The bias correction is
3 only applied for the skill metrics mentioned above. The correlation coefficients shown in this paper are all 95%
4 significant, based on a two-tail Student's *t*-test. Considering the fact that time series of oceanic variable is
5 usually auto-correlated, the "effective sample size" (von Storch and Zwiers 1999) is applied.

6 **Chapter 3 Evaluation of decadal predictive skill of sea surface temperature**

7 Working as a control parameter for the heat flux exchanges between the atmosphere and the ocean, SST is a key
8 variable in climate research. It therefore has been used as a primary assessment parameter of the skill arising
9 from initialization. Respective skill improvement can be observed in particular over parts of the ocean in recent
10 studies of decadal prediction (e.g. Pohlmann et al. 2009; Mochizuki et al. 2010, 2012; Matei et al. 2012). SST is
11 used here again to assess the initialized forecasts in terms of regions and duration of predictive skill.

12 At lead year 1, wide areas with significant prediction skill are observed over almost the whole ocean from the
13 maps of ACC between CIH and CDA (Fig 2). The highest ACC skill is found near the tropical area of the ocean,
14 especially over the eastern tropical Pacific, where many forecasts failed to capture the variability (e.g. Matei et al.
15 2012; Pohlmann et al. 2009; Polkova et al. 2014). Predictive skill at the first lead year is mostly achieved due to
16 initialization. The consistent dynamics and compatibility of initial conditions (CDA) with the model CFES used
17 for hindcasts ensure the high SST predictive skill in CIH.

18 However, as the forecast evolves, the influence from initialization decreases, while the response to externally
19 forced climate variation starts to influence the forecasts (Hawkins and Sutton 2009; Branstator and Teng 2010,
20 2012). A significant decrease of skill is observed when the lead time of the forecasts increases to lead year 2-5
21 and 6-9, especially over the North Pacific and tropical Pacific, where significant skill is observed at lead year 1.
22 Some areas with predictive skill in the southern Indian Ocean and sub-polar Southern Ocean still remain at lead
23 year 2-5 for CIH/CDA. Nevertheless, researchers do report less prediction skill over the North Pacific compared
24 with the Indian Ocean (e.g. Goddard et al. 2013; Doblas-Reyes et al. 2013). Studies show that initialization is
25 playing a more significant role in predictive skill than the uninitialized simulations in the Pacific (Guémas et al.
26 2013; Meehl and Teng 2012, 2014). However, the sensitivity to uncertainties from the initial state (Branstator et
27 al. 2012; Branstator and Teng 2012) may cause a decrease in predictive skill in the Pacific. The small uncertainty
28 in initial conditions in CIH leads to high predictability over eastern tropical Pacific at lead year 1.

1 For the GECCO2 initialized hindcasts (GIH), the patterns in terms of SST anomaly correlation coefficients skill
2 (Fig 3) are similar to those of CIH, but with much smaller areas of significant SST predictive skill. The figure
3 reveals the highest SST predictive skill in the southern tropical Indian Ocean, the sub-polar Southern Ocean and
4 the western Pacific at lead year 1. CIH shows higher correlation with CDA than GIH does with GECCO2,
5 especially over the eastern tropical Pacific. Poor SST predictive skill over the tropical Pacific at lead year 1 is
6 observed in previous studies (e.g. Matei et al. 2012; Pohlmann et al. 2009) from GECCO initialized hindcasts,
7 mainly due to the permission of a relatively large SST error while nudging the model towards GECCO
8 (Pohlmann et al. 2009). Later on, in an attempt to improve the predictive skill of SST in the tropics, Pohlmann et
9 al. (2013) introduced atmospheric initialization which contributes to the improvement of predictive skill,
10 suggesting atmospheric initialization is necessary in climate prediction. For GIH, instead of nudging GECCO2
11 towards the model CFES first, the hindcasts are directly initialized in the ocean from GECCO2 and in the
12 atmospheric from CDA, which does not allow the atmosphere to adjust to the GECCO2 ocean state. The climate
13 difference between GECCO2 and CDA is likely to cause the atmosphere to be inconsistent with the ocean initial
14 state and leads to model drift. As is indicated by Fig 1 (middle panel), global SST is warm-biased at lead year 1
15 in GIH. The spatial distribution of the mean SST difference (Fig 4) between CDA/GECCO2 and HadISST shows
16 that GECCO2 (bottom panel) is warmer than CDA (top panel) in the tropical Pacific (with an exception of
17 central Pacific along the equator), while such differences are less in the high latitudes. The large bias in the
18 tropical Pacific may explain the relatively lower SST predictive skill of GIH relative to CIH there. Spatial
19 distribution of RMSE based on annual mean SST from GECCO2 or CDA and HadISST further reveals relatively
20 larger values in GECCO2 than in CDA over the ITCZ area except the central Pacific (not shown). Averaged over
21 the area of 20°S-20°N, 140°E-90°W, GECCO2 has a RMS SST error of 0.49, which is less than the error of
22 HadISST. Spatial distribution of anomaly correlation coefficients indicates that, despite the warm bias in
23 GECCO2, GECCO2 is better correlated with HadISST than CDA (Fig 5). Therefore, the use of GECCO2 as an
24 initial condition for the forecasts is probably mainly affected by a larger bias in the tropics which will be
25 investigated further below.

26 For the 4-year average, significant SST predictive skill is also found over part of the Indian Ocean and the
27 western tropical Pacific. Both GIH and CIH fail to capture the long-term variation of SST over the North
28 Atlantic (NA), where other studies reported robust skill for forecasts initialized through different modeling
29 systems (e.g. Polkova et al. 2014; Matei et al. 2012; Yang et al. 2013). In the North Atlantic, although the

1 relative role of internal variability and external forcing on SST predictive skill remains a topic to debate, the role
2 of external forcing (including volcanic eruptions and anthropogenic aerosols) is non-negligible (e.g. Booth et al.
3 2012; Dunstone et al. 2013; Otterå et al. 2010; Villarini and Vecchi 2013). The predictive skill of SST in the
4 North Atlantic is therefore affected by removing the trend, which is connected with increasing GHG but also
5 related to multi-decadal variability. Further analysis on non-detrended SST indicates significant SST prediction
6 skill in GIH (not shown) over the North Atlantic until lead years 6-9, while the NA SST predictive skill in CIH is
7 slightly affected. On the other hand, a recent study by Müller et al. (2014) pointed out that a larger period of
8 hindcasts enhances the significant predictive skill of the NA SST at decadal time scales, due to inclusion of
9 additional phases of multi-decadal variability. Compared with extended hindcasts of 1901-2010, the trend is
10 more important than the internal variability for the NA SST predictive skill of the shorter hindcasts (1960-2010).
11 As is indicated above, the evaluation period in our solution is restricted to an even shorter 27-years period
12 (1980-2006), due to the available CDA synthesis, which is only half size of the 50-years period that are
13 commonly used by previous studies. The reduced predictive skill of the North Atlantic SST in our solution is
14 partly due to detrending and thresholds for significance are high due to the relatively short hindcast period.

15 In summary, the above results indicate that when the long-term linear trend is removed, dynamical consistent
16 initial conditions provide higher predictive skill of SST than when initialized with initial states from a different
17 model. The strongest enhancement of skill is achieved globally in the first year, especially over the eastern
18 tropical Pacific. However, for longer lead periods the difference becomes small. Surprisingly, the analysis of the
19 non-detrended SST shows that the trend, and thus potentially the forced part of the signal, is less well
20 represented when initialized with consistent initial conditions.

21 **Chapter 4 Mechanism leading to low prediction skill**

22 Climate predictive skill at shorter time scales is strongly influenced by initialization. Therefore, predictive skill is
23 mostly affected by initialization during the first lead year. From the above results, the most significant difference
24 is that CIH shows substantially higher correlations over the tropical Pacific at the first lead year than GIH. This
25 makes the tropical Pacific a suitable region to assess the impact of consistency between the climate model and
26 its initial conditions on forecast skill and explore the underlying mechanism. Therefore, we will now focus on
27 this region to find out how a non-consistent initial condition influences forecast skills.

28 Because in the tropical Pacific, interannual climate variability is highly characterized by ENSO (El Niño-
29 Southern Oscillation), the high/low predictive skill of tropical Pacific SST from CIH/GIH at the first lead year is

1 possibly related to ENSO events. Therefore, we now explore the possible mechanism regarding the predictive
2 skill of hindcast SST through analyzing key characteristics of the El Niño and investigate why this mechanism
3 seems to work differently between different initialization approaches. For this purpose, the Niño 3.4 Index based
4 on SST anomalies in the Niño 3.4 region (170°W-120°W, 5°S-5°N) is chosen to characterize the evolution of
5 ENSO events.

6 **4.1 Predictive skill of El Niño events**

7 By comparing the time series of the hindcast monthly Niño 3.4 Index during the first lead year to that of
8 HadISST (Fig 6), it becomes obvious that CIH reproduces ENSO events for most of the hindcasts at the first lead
9 year. However, besides the successfully reproduced historical ENSO events, some additional erroneous El Niño
10 events are also detected, especially for GIH. CIH produces only one El Niño-like event in 1984, while GIH
11 produces 8 more—1980, 1981, 1984, 1985, 1989, 1996, 2001, 2003 and 2005. Hovmöller diagrams of sea
12 surface height (SSH) and zonal wind stress (τ_x) over these years (not shown) indicate similar characteristics and
13 development procedure as historical El Niño (not shown). However, observations of tropical Pacific SST do not
14 indicate occurrence of El Niño during these years. This leads to a conclusion that GIH produces pseudo El Niño
15 events. These pseudo-ENSO events account for one third of the number of forecasts. Apparently the poor
16 predictive skill of SST of GIH is relevant to these erroneous El Niño events. In the following, we therefore
17 investigate what conditions in the GECCO2 state lead to the reproduction of pseudo El Niño events in GIH and
18 how the problem can be addressed.

19 **4.2 Zonal momentum balance in the upper equatorial Pacific**

20 In climate prediction, a state resulting from assimilating data into an ocean model is commonly used for
21 initializing the model. When combining this ocean state with the atmospheric model, the balance between the
22 zonal pressure gradient and wind stress forcing near the equator needs special attention. Bell et al. (2004)
23 describes the lack of this balance during data assimilation as one of the reasons for artificial model response. By
24 initializing the CFES coupled model with the interpolated GECCO2 ocean state and the atmospheric conditions
25 from the CFES model based CDA, differences between the atmospheric state of GECCO2 and CDA model may
26 lead to an imbalance between the zonal wind stress and pressure gradient force in the equatorial Pacific. If the
27 imbalance is large, conditions resembling the early phase of an El Niño event could appear. In order to explore
28 the low performance of GIH in predicting the equatorial Pacific SST, we will focus on the balance along the
29 equator between the pressure gradient force (PGF hereafter) and surface zonal wind stress τ_x for CIH vs GIH in

1 the upper ocean. Following [Bryden et al. \(1985\)](#), the governing equation of momentum balance in the upper
2 equatorial Pacific in the x -direction under balanced situation can be written as:

$$3 \quad A_v \frac{\partial u}{\partial z} = \frac{1}{\rho_0} (\tau^x - \int_0^z \frac{\partial P}{\partial x} dz)$$

$$4 \quad P = \rho g \eta + \int_z^\eta \rho' dz$$

5 where A_v is the vertical eddy viscosity, u is the zonal velocity. The left-hand term represents the
6 parameterization of the vertical mixing due to uncompensated surface wind stress. Here η is the sea surface
7 height, P is the pressure and ρ is the density of the seawater. ρ' in the equation is the difference between ρ and
8 ρ_0 ($\rho_0 = 1026 \text{ kg/m}^3$). At the depth where the vertical shear of zonal velocity becomes zero, the wind stress is
9 compensated by the integrated pressure gradient force ([Bryden et al. 1985](#)). Since the simplest early models for
10 predicting El Niño rely on statistical relations of the balance between wind stress and gradients of density
11 ([Barnett et al. 1988](#)), we illustrate the change in balance of monthly-mean GECCO2 Synthesis as a reference.

12 The residual between pressure gradient force and zonal wind stress along the equatorial Pacific is illustrated in
13 Fig 7 in two categories: historical El Niño years and non-El Niño years. As can be seen, a negative imbalance is
14 already observed in December of the previous year in the western Pacific in historical El Niño years. From
15 March on, a strong negative imbalance has developed in the western equatorial Pacific. The uncompensated
16 negative imbalance could possibly result from 1) relatively weak easterly trade winds; 2) strong pressure
17 gradient force or the combination of 1) and 2). The imbalance propagates eastwards as Kelvin wave until it
18 reaches the eastern Pacific, which is in agreement with the developing phase of El Niño. As a result, warm
19 anomalies are observed in the eastern Pacific (not shown), with a peak intensity around November and lately
20 disappearance of the imbalance. Since the simulations of CIH and GIH are initialized in January, a possible
21 imbalance in January between zonal wind stress and pressure gradient force serves as one condition to trigger an
22 ENSO event later in the year. On the other hand, an imbalance introduced in January is still likely to propagate
23 as Kelvin wave and therefore may explain the occurrence of those pseudo El Niños observed in GIH.

24 Considering pseudo El Niño events produced in GIH, we study the zonal momentum balance of GIH in three
25 categories 1) historical El Niño years 2) pseudo El Niño years and 3) the non-El Niño years. Since CIH produces
26 only one pseudo El Niño in 1984, this year is excluded in the two categories for CIH and the residual of
27 momentum balance of CIH will be assessed in two categories as the GECCO2 Synthesis. However, although the

1 pressure gradient force and wind stress are the main terms of the momentum balance in the equatorial Pacific,
2 they do not perfectly balance and further terms are relevant, in particular, the vertical advection of the zonal
3 momentum which has opposite sign in the eastern and the western tropical Pacific. In order to exclude the
4 advection terms from the balance, the momentum balance shown in Fig 8 is referred to those averaged over non-
5 El Niño years in January. Due to the atmospheric pressure forcing embedded in the coupled climate model CFES,
6 the effects of sea surface air pressure on sea surface height are removed from the hindcasts.

7 As indicated by the black lines in Fig 8, in historical El Niño years, negative values between PGF and τ_x are
8 observed in the central equatorial Pacific in January for CIH and GIH. The averaged zonal momentum imbalance
9 in GIH during its pseudo El Niño years also shows a negative value over large area of western and central
10 equatorial Pacific (blue line in Fig 8), in January when the forecast is initialized. However, the evolution of
11 negative imbalance is sensitive to perturbations and develops inconsistently and differently from the GECCO2
12 Synthesis (Fig 7), the eastwards propagation of the imbalance is hardly visible along the equator (not shown).
13 Within the hindcast period of 1980-2006, there are only 7 historical El Niño events and 8 pseudo El Niño events.
14 Due to the small sample size the variability of the events leads to an inconsistent imprint on the imbalance,
15 which together with the fact that in January the lead-time to the fully developed El Niño is large and indications
16 are therefore weak makes the identifications of the causes of El Niño difficult. However, the similarity between
17 the real and pseudo-events suggests that the imbalance in January is the relevant cause.

18 The offset in the balance for GIH at initial time suggests that a larger pressure gradient exists in GECCO2 than
19 what can be balanced by the wind stress from CDA, which implies difference in SSH and consequently
20 thermocline slope and SST gradients. These individual elements affecting the momentum balance at the
21 initialization state are investigated in two categories, as is the case for GECCO2.

22 The climatological SSH and SST anomaly along the equatorial Pacific in January are shown in Fig 9 from four
23 different data sources: GECCO2 (red), CDA (green), GIH (black), and CIH (blue), in two categories as is
24 mentioned above. The anomalies are calculated relative to the CDA averaged over non-El Niño years. The blue
25 lines almost overlap the green lines in the four panels, suggesting that CIH well resembles CDA. However, the
26 black and red lines don't follow each other, indicating that GIH has already moved away from GECCO2 despite
27 the short period after initialization. During pseudo El Niño years, GECCO2 shows larger zonal SSH and SST
28 gradients along the equator in the January than CDA (Fig 9, a and c), with a warmer/colder core in the

1 western/eastern Pacific. The relatively larger zonal SSH/SST gradients are also observed in GIH, which supports
2 the occurrence of pseudo El Niños later in those years.

3 Targeting the problem of ENSO prediction, so far there are three indicators of El Niño during spring, for the
4 occurrence of El Niño later in the year, which include the Meridional Mode (MM, Chang et al. 2007), the
5 equatorial heat content and the westerly wind bursts (e.g. Kug et al. 2005; Jin 1997). The first is considered as a
6 conduit for the extratropical atmosphere to impact ENSO (e.g. Chang et al. 2007; Wang et al. 2012) and
7 describes a pattern of warming and southwesterly wind anomalies in the vicinity of the Intertropical
8 Convergence Zone. Each of the latter two factors by itself is a necessary but not sufficient pre-condition for an
9 El Niño. In the tropics, there is a solid relationship between the variability of the ocean heat content (OHC) and
10 sea-level variations (White and Tai 1995; Fu and Cazenave 2000). Such solid relationship is proved by the large
11 values of correlation coefficients (0.71 to 0.93) between OHC (upper 500m) over the tropics (5°N-5°S) and SSH
12 along the equator from GECCO2, suggesting that SSH can be used as proxy for OHC to evaluate its impact on
13 ENSO. Therefore, patterns associated with the Meridional Mode are considered to enhance the perspective for El
14 Niño prediction.

15 The difference of SST between GECCO2 and CDA reveals a warming anomaly during the pseudo El Niño
16 years (Fig 10, Fig 9c), whilst the southwesterly wind anomaly only occurs in the central Pacific and northern
17 subtropical Pacific. Therefore, during pseudo El Niño years of GIH, different ocean states between CDA and
18 GECCO2 imply different responses. As is shown in Fig 11 (a), stronger zonal wind stress is observed in
19 GECCO2 in the central Pacific (180°-140°W) compared with CDA. Larger mean zonal pressure gradient than
20 CDA in the area of 175°-130°W (Fig 10, b) is also observed in GECCO2. A stronger wind in the central Pacific
21 is needed to balance the relatively larger zonal SSH/SST gradient along the equator from GECCO2 in GIH.
22 Hence, an adjustment between the ocean and atmosphere through coupled air-sea interaction for GIH is taking
23 place and the imbalance propagates eastwards as Kelvin waves along the equator, causing the occurrence of
24 pseudo El Niños.

25 **4.3 Case study with anomaly initialization**

26 The approach of anomaly initialization helps in reducing model drifts (Fig 1) by constraining the model with
27 observed anomalies superimposed on the model climatology (e.g. Smith et al. 2013). Previous studies (e.g.
28 Polkova et al. 2014) showed improved SST predictive skill in the tropical Pacific with the anomaly initialization
29 strategy. Therefore, by initializing the model with observed anomalies added to the model climate (here we take

1 the climatology of 20C simulation), the warm bias along the tropical Pacific could be reduced in AGIH and the
2 balance between zonal pressure gradient and wind stress forcing should be expected.

3 The spatial distribution of the anomaly correlation coefficients for detrended SST (Fig 12) denotes predictive
4 skill in part of the central Pacific and along the western Pacific at the first lead year in AGIH. Consistent with
5 that, the monthly Niño 3.4 Index of lead year 1 (Fig 6) shows that AGIH reproduces historical El Niño events
6 better than GIH. In all, there are 3 erroneous El Niño events produced in AGIH, compared to 9 events in GIH.
7 The successful reproduction of ENSO explains the predictive skill of SST in the tropical Pacific at lead year 1 in
8 AGIH. Further illustration of the momentum balance between pressure gradient force and zonal wind stress in
9 the upper equatorial Pacific denotes a negative imbalance along the equatorial Pacific during the climatological
10 January of the historical El Niño years. The usage of anomaly initialization strategy in AGIH guarantees the
11 compatibility between the ocean and the atmospheric model by initializing the ocean from a state that is closer to
12 the model climate. The balanced state in AGIH in January over non-El Niño years supports the interpretation
13 that the incompatibility of GECCO2 mean climate leads to the dynamical momentum imbalance in the upper
14 equatorial Pacific in GIH. This highlights the importance of a momentum balance between pressure gradient
15 force and wind stress for SST predictive skill in the equatorial Pacific at shorter time scales.

16 **Chapter 5 Concluding Remarks**

17 In this paper, the benefit of initializing a decadal prediction system with dynamically consistent initial conditions
18 is explored by comparing respective results obtained by initializing the coupled model CFES with the
19 atmospheric initial conditions from CDA and the ocean states either from CDA or from a non-native ocean
20 component (GECCO2). In terms of predictability of SST, we find that CIH provides higher predictive skill at
21 lead year 1 over vast areas of the ocean, suggesting that the dynamical consistency of initial conditions is
22 relevant for the predictive skill at least in the first lead year. The most significant improvement is observed in
23 CIH over the tropical Pacific. The difference between two different hindcasts becomes small over longer lead
24 periods. At longer lead times, the importance of the response to externally forcing starts to increase which is
25 mainly seen if time series are not detrended, especially for GIH.

26 At lead year 1, the significant, high SST predictive skill over the tropical Pacific in CIH is connected to a good
27 reproduction of El Niño events while the poor predictive skill of SST of GIH relates to additional erroneous El
28 Niño events. The upper equatorial Pacific Ocean is characterized by a zonal momentum balance between the
29 wind stress and the pressure-gradient force. GIH is initialized with the GECCO2 ocean state but atmospheric

1 conditions are resulted from the same coupled model as used in the hindcasts. Since the ocean state of GECCO2
2 is characterized by a warmer SST with larger zonal SST and SSH gradient than those of CDA, a larger zonal
3 pressure gradient is introduced to GIH. Because the wind stress there remains relatively weaker due to
4 atmospheric initialization through CDA, the large zonal pressure gradient cannot be balanced by wind stress for
5 GIH in the central Pacific. As a result, adjustment through coupled air-sea interaction takes place.

6 The imbalance propagates eastwards as Kelvin waves and causes the additional erroneous El Niños in GIH.
7 Although the two main terms of wind stress and pressure gradient do not perfectly balance and further terms are
8 relevant, in particular, the vertical advection of the zonal momentum which has opposite sign in the eastern and
9 the western tropical Pacific, the reduced predictive skill of GIH in the equatorial Pacific is found mainly related
10 to the dynamical imbalance due to inappropriate oceanic initialization. Our results suggest that in climate
11 predictions, it is beneficial to initialize a model with oceanic initial conditions consistent to the atmospheric state
12 particularly for the predictive skill in the tropical Pacific. Although not quite reaching the skill of the consistently
13 initialized hindcasts of CIH, the anomaly initialization method solves the problem of inconsistent climatological
14 states between the atmosphere and the ocean that offsets the balance between pressure and wind stress in the
15 equatorial Pacific and the excessive number of El Niños is avoided. It should be mentioned that in the commonly
16 used procedure of nudging the ocean to an ocean synthesis the atmosphere is allowed to respond to the ocean
17 state, which will partially make up for differences in climatological states. This also applies to the alternative
18 approach of forcing a coupled model with observed wind in which the ocean is allowed to react to the prescribed
19 wind (Thoma et al. 2015). However, initializing the ocean and the atmosphere simultaneously by nudging both
20 components to the respective reanalyses was shown not provide additional skill in comparison to initializing only
21 the ocean component, particularly in the tropical regions (Pohlmann et al. 2013). A consistent initialization
22 remains therefore an important factor, and to improve tropical predictive skill the momentum balance between
23 zonal wind stress and pressure gradient force along the equatorial Pacific is crucial when initializing the model
24 from any oceanic state.

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- 1 **Table caption**
- 2 Table 1 Summary of the experiments

1

Table 1 Summary of the experiments

Experiments	Initialization	Forecast period	Initial condition	Forcing	realization
20C [*]	Jan of 1946	1946-2007	1980-CDA	GHG, Aerosol, volcano	1
CIH^a	Jan of each year	1980-2007	CDA, full state	GHG, Aerosol, volcano	1
GIH^b	Jan of each year	1980-2007	GECCO2, full state	GHG, Aerosol, volcano	1
AGIH^c	Jan of each year	1980-2007	Ano _{GECCO2+Clim20C} , anomaly	GHG, Aerosol, volcano	1

2 a) CIH: CDA initialized hindcasts

3 b) GIH: GECCO2 initialized hindcasts

4 c) AGIH: GECCO2 initialized hindcasts, with anomaly initialization strategy

1 **Figure Caption**

2 **Fig 1** The time series of global-averaged (60°S-60°N) annual mean SST of HadISST (green), initialized
3 hindcasts (colours) and ocean estimation from which the hindcasts are initialized (CDA/GECCO2/combined
4 anomaly, black). The colored lines in the three panels from top to bottom are CIH, GIH and AGIH

5 **Fig 2** Spatial distribution of SST anomaly correlation coefficient between CIH and CDA (left), and CIH and
6 observed SST (HadISST, right), at lead year 1 (top panels), averages of lead year 2-5(middle panels) and lead
7 year 6-9 (bottom panels). Only the significant coefficients (at 95% level) are shown here. A linear trend removal
8 is applied to all the SST involved before calculation of ACC

9 **Fig 3** Spatial distribution of the SST anomaly correlation coefficient between GIH and GECCO2 (left), and GIH
10 and observed SST (right), at lead year 1 (top panels), averages of lead year 2-5 (middle panels) and lead year 6-9
11 (bottom panels). Only the significant correlation coefficients (at 95% level) are shown here

12 **Fig 4** SST difference to HadISST averaged over 1980-2006 for CDA (top panel) and GECCO2 (bottom panel).

13 **Fig 5** Spatial distribution of the anomaly correlation coefficient for annual-mean SST between CDA and
14 HadISST (top), and GECCO2 and HadISST (bottom). Only the significant correlation coefficients (at 95% level)
15 are shown here

16 **Fig 6** Monthly Niño 3.4 Index of lead year 1 from the hindcasts (black), HadISST (green) and the initialization
17 data (red, CDA and GECCO2 respectively), for (a) CIH and CDA, (b) GIH and GECCO2 and (c) AGIH and
18 GECCO2

19 **Fig 7** Zonal momentum balance of upper equatorial Pacific between pressure gradient force and zonal wind
20 stress from GECCO2 Synthesis (1980-2006) averaged in historical El Niño years (black) and the non-El Niño
21 years (red) at: the former December, March, May, July, September and November. The unit is N/m^2

22 **Fig 8** Zonal momentum balance of upper equatorial Pacific between pressure gradient force and zonal wind
23 stress in January from CIH (right panel), GIH (middle panel) and AGIH (left panel). Black lines denote average
24 over January of historical El Niño years, red lines denote those averaged over non-El Niño years, and blue line
25 indicated average over GIH-produced pseudo El Niño years. All the values shown are calculated according to the
26 baseline of average over non-El Niño years in January. The unit is N/m^2

1 **Fig 9** Climatological SSH/SST anomaly along the equatorial Pacific in January of (a) and (c): GIH produced
2 pseudo El Niño years, (b) and (d): historical El Niño years, for GIH (black), GECCO2(red), CDA (green) and
3 CIH (blue). The anomalies are calculated as differences to CDA averaged over non-El Niño years. The units of
4 SSH and SST are *cm* and *°C*

5 **Fig 10** The January SST/wind stress difference between GECCO2 and CDA as an average over pseudo El Niño
6 years. Color shading indicates SST anomaly (*°C*) and the vectors indicates wind stress anomaly (*N/m²*).

7 **Fig 11** Zonal wind stress (a) and zonal pressure gradient (b) along the equatorial Pacific in January averaged
8 over 1) historical El Niño years from GECCO2 (black) , CDA (red) and 20C (green); 2) non-El Niño years from
9 GECCO2 (blue) CDA (cyan) and 20C (magenta). The unit for wind stress is *N/m²*, and for pressure gradient is
10 *P_a/m*

11 **Fig 12** Spatial distribution of the detrended SST anomaly correlation coefficient between AGIH and GECCO2
12 (left), and difference between $ACC_{AGIH/GECCO2}$ and $ACC_{GIH/GECCO2}$ (right), at the first lead year (top panels),
13 averages of lead year 2-5(middle panels) and lead year 6-9 (bottom panels). Only the significant coefficients (at
14 95% level) are shown here

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2 **Fig 1** The time series of global-averaged (60°S-60°N) annual mean SST of HadISST (green), initialized
 3 hindcasts (colours) and ocean estimation from which the hindcasts are initialized (CDA/GECCO2/combined
 4 anomaly, black). The colored lines in the three panels from top to bottom are CIH, GIH and AGIH

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2 **Fig 2** Spatial distribution of SST anomaly correlation coefficient between CIH and CDA (left), and CIH and
 3 observed SST (HadISST, right), at lead year 1 (top panels), averages of lead year 2-5(middle panels) and lead
 4 year 6-9 (bottom panels). Only the significant coefficients (at 95% level) are shown here. A linear trend removal
 5 is applied to all the SST involved before calculation of ACC

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2 **Fig 3** Spatial distribution of the SST anomaly correlation coefficient between GIH and GECCO2 (left), and GIH
 3 and observed SST (right), at lead year 1 (top panels), averages of lead year 2-5 (middle panels) and lead year 6-9
 4 (bottom panels). Only the significant correlation coefficients (at 95% level) are shown here

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2 **Fig 4** SST difference to HadISST averaged over 1980-2006 for CDA (top panel) and GECCO2 (bottom panel).

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2 **Fig 5** Spatial distribution of the anomaly correlation coefficient for annual-mean SST between CDA and
 3 HadISST (top), and GECCO2 and HadISST (bottom). Only the significant correlation coefficients (at 95% level)
 4 are shown here

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2 **Fig 6** Monthly Niño 3.4 Index of lead year 1 from the hindcasts (black), HadISST (green) and the initialization
 3 data (red, CDA and GECCO2 respectively), for (a) CIH and CDA, (b) GIH and GECCO2 and (c) AGIH and
 4 GECCO2

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2 **Fig 7** Zonal momentum balance of upper equatorial Pacific between pressure gradient force and zonal wind
 3 stress from GECCO2 Synthesis (1980-2006) averaged in historical El Niño years (black) and the non-El Niño
 4 years (red) at: the former December, March, May, July, September and November. The unit is N/m^2

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 2 **Fig 8** Zonal momentum balance of upper equatorial Pacific between pressure gradient force and zonal wind
 3 stress in January from CIH (right panel), GIH (middle panel) and AGIH (left panel). Black lines denote average
 4 over January of historical El Niño years, red lines denote those averaged over non-El Niño years, and blue line
 5 indicated average over GIH-produced pseudo El Niño years. All the values shown are calculated according to the
 6 baseline of average over non-El Niño years in January. The unit is N/m^2

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 2 **Fig 9** Climatological SSH/SST anomaly along the equatorial Pacific in January of (a) and (c): GIH produced
 3 pseudo El Niño years, (b) and (d): historical El Niño years, for GIH (black), GECCO2(red), CDA (green) and
 4 CIH (blue). The anomalies are calculated as differences to CDA averaged over non-El Niño years. The units of
 5 SSH and SST are *cm* and *°C*

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2 **Fig 10** The January SST/wind stress difference between GECCO2 and CDA as an average over pseudo El Niño
 3 years. Color shading indicates SST anomaly ($^{\circ}\text{C}$) and the vectors indicates wind stress anomaly (N/m^2).

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2 **Fig 11** Zonal wind stress (a) and zonal pressure gradient (b) along the equatorial Pacific in January averaged
 3 over 1) historical El Niño years from GECCO2 (black) , CDA (red) and 20C (green); 2) non-El Niño years from
 4 GECCO2 (blue) CDA (cyan) and 20C (magenta). The unit for wind stress is N/m^2 , and for pressure gradient is
 5 P_a/m

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2 **Fig 12** Spatial distribution of the detrended SST anomaly correlation coefficient between AGIH and GECCO2
 3 (left), and difference between $ACC_{AGIH/GECCO2}$ and $ACC_{GIH/GECCO2}$ (right), at the first lead year (top panels),
 4 averages of lead year 2-5(middle panels) and lead year 6-9 (bottom panels). Only the significant coefficients (at
 5 95% level) are shown here